

NONIDENTICAL MACHINE SCHEDULING IN FLEXIBLE MANUFACTURING SYSTEM USING RECURRENT NEURAL NETWORK AND GENETIC ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT: This research paper focuses on optimizing the scheduling of jobs and tools for nonidentical machines, emphasizing minimizing makespan. The study employs metaheuristic algorithms to address this challenging combinatorial optimization problem. A comprehensive comparative analysis of different metaheuristic algorithms is conducted to evaluate their effectiveness in achieving this objective. This paper presents the above problem statement, metadata, algorithmic details, and results to provide insights into selecting the most suitable approach for scheduling in nonidentical machine environments. It is observed that the phase 3 modification of the Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) had the lowest makespan metric while also providing a similar accuracy compared to the other algorithms. The accuracy of phase 3 of the Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) is 99.8%, and the average processing time is approximately 4.02 minutes.

KEYWORDS: Artificial intelligence, Flexible manufacturing system, Genetic algorithm, Non-identical machines, Recurrent neural network.

1 INTRODUCTION

In Flexible Manufacturing System FMS setups, it is typical to encounter machines that vary in their processing capabilities and tool setups. Each task within the FMS is associated with a distinct processing time and specific tool requirements. The primary objective revolves around reducing the makespan, which entails efficiently completing all tasks while considering the capabilities of the available machines. The strategic determination of the sequence in which tasks are processed on diverse machines plays a pivotal role in achieving efficient scheduling.

Our objective was to create an innovative scheduling algorithm designed explicitly for a Flexible Manufacturing System (FMS) that utilizes machines with differing characteristics. In order to meet our primary objective, this study focuses on the circumstances of J jobs that must be processed on M nonidentical machines with T shared tool types between the nonidentical machines. The jobs must be allotted in a specific order.

To battle the abovementioned problem, we use various algorithms classified into Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) and Genetic Algorithm (GA). An artificial neural network that handles sequential data is called a recurrent neural network (RNN). RNNs, unlike traditional feedforward neural networks,

include connections that loop around on themselves, allowing them to maintain a recollection of previous inputs, which is referred to as the "hidden state." Because of this characteristic, RNNs can be used in time series prediction, voice recognition, and natural language processing, among other applications. RNNs operate incrementally on input data, with each step's output relying on the present input and the network's previous state, enabling them to manage sequential information and capture temporal dependencies. Under RNN, we have three variations: RNN Phase 1, RNN Phase 2 and RNN Phase 3. The RNN Phase 1 algorithm performs simulations and considers all input configurations, hence mimics the brute force approach. The RNN Phase 2 algorithm reduces the number of input configurations. It keeps the internal processing and functionality similar to that of the RNN Phase 1 algorithm but, in turn, reduces the accuracy. The RNN Phase 3 algorithm aims to reduce the input configurations and maintain accuracy by taking an entirely different approach than the generalized functionality of the RNN algorithm. A genetic algorithm is a computer-based technique that draws inspiration from the evolutionary processes observed in nature. It aids in the search for the most effective solution to a given problem by initiating a population of potential solutions, identifying the top-performing ones, amalgamating them to produce fresh solutions, and

iterating through these steps across numerous generations. Through this repetitive approach, genetic algorithms can uncover the best or nearly ideal solutions for a wide range of intricate problems, encompassing areas like optimization, design, and many others.

The primary objective of FMS optimization is to minimize the makespan, which directly correlates with enhanced production efficiency and decreased operational expenses. As such, it is imperative to thoroughly assess these algorithms in terms of both makespan reduction and computational efficiency. Effective scheduling guarantees the optimal utilization of resources, ultimately improving overall production efficiency. Reducing makespan is paramount for maintaining a competitive edge in today's highly competitive manufacturing landscape. Shorter production cycles enable swift responses to customer demands and can lead to an expanded market share. Efficient scheduling not only ensures quick turnaround times and reliable delivery schedules but also minimizes the need to rush production to meet tight deadlines, thereby reducing the risk of quality issues and allowing for smoother production processes and more time for quality control, thus ensuring that products consistently meet the desired quality standards.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The results of the two-level batch scheduling heuristic (TH), shortest weighted processing time (SWPT) rule, earliest weighted due date (EWDD) rule, and simulated annealing (SA) method were compared, and it was found that the SA method usually produced the best results. The computational tests utilized data from a single compound semiconductor production facility, which may restrict the findings' applicability to other sectors or environments. The research does not address the effect of different parameter values on heuristic performance (Kim et al., 2003).

An evolutionary approach minimizes the makespan in identical machine scheduling challenges. The approach is efficient and suited for larger-scale identical parallel machine scheduling issues, surpassing heuristic and simulated annealing methods (Min & Cheng, 1999). A genetic approach based on random key encoding was developed to tackle the scheduling challenge of minimizing makespan on parallel nonidentical batch processing machines (Alcan & Balişgil, 2012). Using simulation tools, the novel genetic algorithm (GA) was evaluated using a numerical example. The computational outcomes of the GA and the LPT (Longest Processing Time) dispatching rule were

contrasted. The results show that the GA described in the research might reduce the maximum completion time (makespan) for the nonidentical parallel machine scheduling issue (Balin, 2011). The nonidentical parallel machine scheduling problem was tackled with a genetic algorithm (GA) technique integrated into a simulation model to minimize the maximum completion time (makespan) using fuzzy processing times (FPMSP). The proposed genetic algorithm (GA) method produces good results (Balin, 2012). The traditional methods of scheduling are frequently insufficient for handling the intricate, multi-objective nature of FJSP, which calls for the development of sophisticated algorithms like the hybrid Taguchi-genetic approach proposed. This approach includes a novel encoding technique that integrates operation assignment and machine selection into a single chromosome, thereby enabling feasible solutions. The results of various benchmarks show that the proposed HTGA outperforms traditional genetic algorithms in terms of both convergence speed and makespan, demonstrating its efficacy in addressing FJSPs (Chang et al., 2015). Manufacturing systems are frequently subject to unforeseen events, which necessitates the development of efficient integrated plans for production scheduling and maintenance. The proposed model aims to fill this gap by incorporating real-time data into the scheduling and maintenance planning processes. This system is designed to collect real-time data on machine conditions and to update production schedules and maintenance plans as needed in response to this data. The system employs a modified hybrid genetic algorithm (mHGA) to generate optimized plans that can respond to various production disruptions, including job arrivals and machine failures (Ghaleb et al., 2021).

Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) was developed to reduce the weighted tardiness while scheduling nonidentical parallel batch processing machines. In more minor issue instances, the PSO method was shown to be highly competitive, whereas, in bigger problem instances, it produced higher-quality solutions in less time (Hulett et al., 2017).

In computational tests, the Simulated Annealing Algorithm (SA) and the Genetic Algorithm (GA) were contrasted using actual data from a compound semiconductor production plant. The article demonstrated that SA outperformed GA in more complex cases. Other performance measures or goal functions outside Total Weighted Tardiness (TWT) were not included in the research, which may restrict comprehension of the algorithms' performance in varied scheduling contexts (Na et al., 2006).

To overcome job shop/combinatorial scheduling challenges in a flexible manufacturing cell (FMC), it was recommended that the simulated annealing algorithm (SAA) and the priority dispatching rules algorithm (PDRA) be employed as heuristic techniques. Although SAA's processing time is longer than PDRA's, it is justified for previous planning situations (Prabaharan et al., 2006).

Non-traditional optimization methodologies such as memetic algorithm (MA), genetic algorithm (GA), particle swarm algorithm (PSA), and simulated annealing (SA) algorithm were suggested to handle the scheduling problem in flexible manufacturing systems (FMS). The paper's findings show that the particle swarm algorithm (PSA) is the most effective method for handling the scheduling problem in flexible manufacturing systems (FMS). It accomplishes the most minor combined goal function and produces outcomes closer to the global optimum in less time (Jerald et al., 2005).

A scatter-search (SS) meta-heuristic method was utilized for schedule optimization of flexible manufacturing systems, considering multiple objectives, such as minimizing idle time and penalty costs for not meeting due dates simultaneously. The scatter-search approach outperforms other methods, such as the genetic algorithm, simulated annealing algorithm, mimetic algorithm, and particle swarm algorithm (Saravanan & Haq, 2008).

An efficient discrete differential evolution (DDE) approach was suggested for dealing with the scheduling problem of uniform parallel batch processing machines with nonidentical capacity and unexpected job sizes. In terms of solution quality and resilience, the suggested discrete differential evolution (DDE) approach beat a random keys genetic algorithm (RKGGA), a commercial solver (CPLEX), and a particle swarm optimization (PSO) technique, particularly for large-scale examples. The article does not consider other objectives, such as total completion time and overall tardiness, which may be essential in real-world settings (Zhou et al., 2016).

The flexible job shop scheduling problem (FJSSP) is a highly complex and challenging problem that requires efficient optimization techniques due to its NP-hard nature and the exponential growth of possible sequences as the problem size increases. This paper presents hybrid algorithms that enhance both global and local search efficiency while reducing computational time and dependency on initial conditions. The proposed hybrid approaches, ePSOGSA and ePSOGA, aim to simultaneously minimize makespan, maximum workload, and total workload. The performance of these hybrid approaches was tested on various

benchmark instances, and the results demonstrated superior performance in minimizing idle time and achieving better objective values compared to standard algorithms (Bharti & Jain, 2020).

A branch and bound technique was devised to minimize regular total cost functions for scheduling work on unrelated parallel machines. The branch and bound approach, which incorporates reduction and bounding techniques, increases the performance of scheduling jobs for unrelated parallel machines to minimize significantly regular total cost functions. Other objective functions, such as makespan and total completion time, should be considered in the article (Azizoglu & Kirca, 1999).

The scheduling of n single operation jobs with an expected due date on m nonidentical machines was proposed, which reduces the problem to a transportation problem that a polynomial time algorithm can solve. In the case of identical machines, it also minimizes the absolute lateness problem by presenting a heuristic technique to minimize makespan across all schedules. The findings demonstrate that the suggested models and algorithms can efficiently minimize the sum of the absolute lateness and the makespan when scheduling jobs with a shared due date on nonidentical and identical machines (Alidaee & Panwalkar, 1993). In order to minimize the makespan of parallel machines with nonidentical capacities when scheduling jobs with similar processing times, a polynomial-time approximation approach (technology A1) was developed. The paper's computer experiment reveals that the approximation method (method A2) functions well in practice. The study does not include a complete examination of algorithm A1 and algorithm A2 performance in terms of worst-case ratios and performance in diverse issue situations (Wang & Leung, 2014).

A framework for scheduling in a flexible manufacturing system that employs parallel neural networks to make decisions on due date assignments, dispatching criteria, and resource availability was proposed. In the flexible manufacturing system, batch processing of artificial neural networks trained in the study provided alternate options for resource availability, due date assignments, and dispatching rules. These solutions were tested by modeling the production system again and comparing performance metrics. The findings revealed that the FCFS (First-Come-First-Served) priority rule was the most effective in meeting the performance targets (Yildirim et al., 2006).

A unique technique termed the constraint-based genetic algorithm (CBGA) was introduced to address the machine-loading problem of a flexible manufacturing system (FMS). The proposed

constraint-based genetic algorithm (CBGA) outperforms simple genetic algorithm-based heuristics regarding constraint violations and the number of generations required (Kumar et al., 2006).

An evolutionary method based on the AIS (Artificial Immune System) generates optimum schedules to minimize makespan. It employs heuristic processes to establish the optimal sequence that minimizes the makespan through task, machine, and tool selection (Raj et al., 2014).

In a nonidentical parallel-machine environment, a Genetic Algorithm-Fuzzy Logic Approach (GA-Fuzzy) was given to choose the optimal weighted earliness-tardiness combinations. The performance of the proposed GA-Fuzzy technique's combined objective function was compared to solutions obtained by genetic algorithm (GA) techniques known as GA with Multi-Component Uniform Order-based Crossover Generator (GA-MCUOX) and GA with Partially Mapped Crossover Operator (GA-PMX). According to the comparison, the suggested GA-Fuzzy approach beats both GA-PMX and GA-MCUOX (Raja et al., 2008).

In order to tackle the order acceptance and scheduling problem in a nonidentical parallel machine environment, a Lagrangian relaxation approach was devised. The technique updates the Lagrangian multipliers using a cutting-edge approach and a heuristic method to find viable solutions. In addition, the authors suggest a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) formulation to maximize profit and a globalized robust counterpart (GRC) of the MILP model to deal with variable revenue and processing times. The simulation analysis revealed that the MILP model's globalized robust counterpart (GRC) performed better on average than its traditional robust equivalent. The numerical simulation results show that the suggested Lagrangian relaxation approach effectively tackles moderate-to-large-scale instances of the order acceptance and scheduling issue (Emami et al., 2016). The proposition of novel methodologies for optimizing scheduling in advanced flexible manufacturing environments through the utilization of mixed integer linear programming (MILP) models was put forth. This approach aims to address the intricacies associated with multitasking machines equipped with multiple spindles and turrets. The MILP model was scrutinized in small-scale instances, demonstrating its efficacy in optimal scheduling for up to six jobs and three machines. The findings revealed that the model exhibited varying degrees of efficiency based on the number of machines, with optimal performance achieved in smaller instances (Naderi & Azab, 2015).

A heuristic method aimed at minimizing makespan, by allowing operations to be processed on multiple machines, making it more complex and NP-hard in a Flexible Job Shop Scheduling Problem (FJSP) was developed (Ziaee, 2014).

The complexity of the dynamic flexible job shop scheduling problem (DFJSP), which involves unpredictable events such as machine breakdowns and new job arrivals, renders traditional scheduling methods insufficient. To assess the effectiveness of the Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS)-based method, a series of experiments were conducted, demonstrating its superior performance in terms of response time and makespan compared to traditional scheduling methods. The aim of the optimization process was to minimize the makespan, while simultaneously allowing operations to be held in an infinite buffer until they are processed (Li et al., 2021).

The incorporation of maintenance into scheduling models, while emphasizing the significance of accounting for machine availability constraints, was examined. A range of preventive maintenance approaches, such as fixed time periods and adaptable windows, were assessed. Additionally, a new adaptable maintenance policy was introduced, which allows for variable starting times. The primary objective function remains the reduction of makespan, while additional objectives, including overall production cost and energy consumption, have gained prominence in recent research. The article presents a local search algorithm designed to address the flexible job shop scheduling problem with maintenance factors, merging heuristic and metaheuristic methodologies (Wocker et al., 2024).

In the papers above, a frequently reoccurring problem was scalability, which stated that the algorithms used could not function well or at all with a variable number of jobs. The second issue observed frequently was the non-applicability of the model to larger and more complex flexible manufacturing systems, which meant that the number of machines and tools needed to be reconfigurable to the desirable number that the client required. Another frequently observed issue was generalizability or robustness, leading to the algorithms working inefficiently with special conditions like boundaries and extreme cases. Lastly, many algorithms do not guarantee an optimal outcome but instead rely on sub-optimal solutions to keep the algorithm's speed from exponentially increasing. We aim to remove at least two or more of these frequently observed issues in our work.

3 METHODOLOGY

The FMS system includes nonidentical machines. Each nonidentical machine in the FMS can process

jobs, but it is constrained to its completion after considering the availability of the tools required to perform operations. Nonidentical machines considered in the FMS have different processing times. We have considered the following input variables as m_j – machines ($j = 1$ to M), where M – total number of nonidentical machines, j_i – jobs ($i = 1$ to J), where J – total number of jobs and t_k – tools ($k = 1$ to T), where T – number of tool types. We have considered 3 nonidentical machines for the FMS system, 4 jobs and 3 tool types. The ratio of processing speed considered for the nonidentical machines $M_1: M_2: M_3$ is 1: 1.2: 1.4. This depicts that the nonidentical machine M_1 has the faster processing speed as compared to the nonidentical machine M_2 which in turn has a faster processing speed as compared to M_3 . In some manufacturing systems, the tools used are costly, so in those cases, only a single copy of the tool is available, i.e., we do not have multiple copies of the same tool. The tools are scheduled so that no two machines can utilize the same tool simultaneously.

3.1 Assumptions

- The order of operations, the required tool types, and the processing times for each operation are predetermined.
- The sequence of operations and the corresponding tools vary from one job to another.
- Each job consists of multiple operations, and each operation requires a specific tool.
- All machines can perform any operation required by the jobs.
- Each machine or tool can process Only one job at a time.
- A job is completed on a single machine, i.e., a job's complete set of operations is executed during a single visit to a machine.
- Operations cannot be interrupted; once initiated, they must be finished.
- Tool availability is treated as a single pool and can be reused for multiple jobs.
- The tool quickly returns to a central tool magazine after an operation, requiring little transfer time, and is then ready for the following operation.

4 DATASET GENERATION

Figure. 1 shows the process of preparing a dataset. Here, N is the number of operations. The constraint for N is that the number of operations will equal 3 for 75% of cases, 2 for 20%, and 1 for 5%. D is a list storing the processing time required for a single job, and its length equals N . Each value in list D lies between 0 and 20 and is distributed with an equal probability. T is a list storing the order of the tools required for a single job and has a length equal to N . It stores a random sequence of values, 1, 2 and 3. The next step is to create a record (rec) and assign the order of the tools to the processing times of each operation for each job. If the number of operations in a job is less than 3, then we append 'X' to the record. Penultimately, we take the sum of the processing times, create a hash, and postpone and prepone the record with the respective values. Lastly, we create two more records with processing times scaled at a ratio of 1.2 and 1.4, and we append the original and the two new records to the table. After sorting the table using the hash values, the dataset is ready. Table 1 shows the data generated for the second record.

5 PROPOSED METHOD AND IMPLEMENTATION

5.1 RNN Phase 1

Fig. 2 shows the RRN Phase 1 model for solving the FMS scheduling problem. In the first iteration, an initial random input sequence is generated, which undergoes simulation, and the output of the simulation is stored as S_1 ; the same random input sequence is modified and undergoes simulation, after which the output of the simulation is compared with S_1 and the outcome with the lower makespan is considered for the following iterations. So, every input configuration is brute forced. In every iteration, the RNN phase 1 learns a different rule and validates the different rules in each iteration. Here, most of the input configurations are expected. The drawback is that too many input configurations lead to prolonged processing times for each simulation.

Fig. 1 Dataset Generation.

Table 1. Data generated for second record.

Hash	Record number	Machine number	Job number	Operation - 1	Operation - 2	Operation - 3	Total Processing Time
211	2	1	1	10(2)	9(1)	20(3)	39
212	2	1	2	8(3)	8(1)	1(2)	17
213	2	1	3	5(3)	11(2)	5(1)	21
214	2	1	4	13(3)	4(1)	X	17
221	2	2	1	12.0(2)	10.8(1)	24.0(3)	46.8
222	2	2	2	9.6(3)	9.6(1)	1.2(2)	20.4
223	2	2	3	6.0(3)	13.2(2)	6.0(1)	25.2
224	2	2	4	15.6(3)	4.8(1)	X	20.4
231	2	3	1	14.0(2)	12.6(1)	28.0(3)	54.6
232	2	3	2	11.2(3)	11.2(1)	1.4(2)	23.8
233	2	3	3	7.0(3)	15.4(2)	7.0(1)	29.4
234	2	3	4	18.2(3)	5.6(1)	X	23.8

5.2 RNN Phase 2

In RNN Phase 1, as the number of input configurations was high, obtaining the solution was also prolonged. The method of eliminating comparatively improbable cases was considered to reduce the time. The limitation was that when the

number of input configurations was decreased, the accuracy declined because it failed to provide the ideal scheduling sequence, offering only a pseudo-optimal solution in 14.4% for 500 input configurations. The reason behind RNN Phase 2 not providing the optimal solution was that the optimal solution was eliminated as it was non-probabilistic.

Fig. 2 RNN Phase 1

5.3 RNN Phase 3

The drawback of the RNN Phase 1 and RNN Phase 2 algorithms was that they used more input configurations to obtain the optimal solution, which took much time to process the simulation. Hence, in RNN Phase 3, it was decided not to consider simulations to get the output and to use an equation to get the output sequences without binding the machines and the jobs at the initial stage of the code. The equation generated to find the number of possibilities is as follows:

$$n! (1 + {}^n C_2) \tag{1}$$

where n is the number of jobs.

Scheduling two jobs might require the same tool, which means one machine has to wait for the tool to be available. To achieve this, it was decided to consider the downtime and delay of the jobs while scheduling the jobs to the machines. Downtime is the sum of time calculated when either one of the machines is waiting for another machine to complete an ongoing job. In contrast, delay is when a machine must wait for another machine once it has completed all the assigned jobs.

Fig. 3 shows the RRN Phase 3 model for solving the FMS scheduling problem. Initially, the first input configuration is taken, and the downtimes are compared. The downtime time of job 1 (P_1) in the sequence is compared with that of job 2, job 3, and job 4 in the sequence. The job whose downtime is minimal is considered a second job (P_2). Now, (P_1) and (P_2) are compared for the minimum and maximum downtime with the remaining two jobs; the job that has minimum downtime is assigned as (P_3), and the job that has maximum downtime is assigned as (P_4). Here, we will get four different input job sequences (Sequence1, Sequence2, Sequence3, and Sequence4), as we have four different variations of initial job 1 (P_1). Once these four job sequences are obtained, we input this sequence of jobs into various structures. A structure is a way in which we can arrange the jobs. The number of possible structures is calculated using the following equation:

$$(1 + {}^n C_2) \tag{2}$$

where n is the number of jobs.

So now we perform simulations for all the calculated structures and assign jobs to machines.

For each sequence, we will get a makespan value (MS1, MS2, MS3 and MS4). Then, these 4 makespan values are compared, and the minimum makespan is obtained as the structure's output makespan for that

particular structure. The minimum values for the various structure's output scores are calculated, and the structure with the least output makespan is considered the final

outcome sequence for that particular input configuration.

Fig. 3 RNN Phase 3

5.4 Genetic Algorithm

In the genetic algorithm, we have population, input configurations; chromosome, one record of those input configurations; and gene, which is a

value from a record. We find the number of possibilities using the equation:

$$n! (1 + {}^nC_2)$$

Fig. 4 Genetic Algorithm

Fig. 4 shows the genetic algorithm for solving the FMS scheduling problem. From each possibility, we will get a rule. During its first iteration, it will provide rule 1; during its second iteration, it will

provide rule 2; and during its third iteration, it will provide rule 3. Once these three rules are generated, they are ranked, and the rule with the best fit will be selected for mutation. After mutation, we will have a

new rule Rm1, which will be considered in the next iteration, and the process follows for every unique possibility. In Flexible Manufacturing System FMS setups, it is typical to encounter machines that vary in their processing capabilities and tool setups. Each task within the FMS is associated with a distinct processing time and specific tool requirements. The primary objective revolves around reducing the makespan, which entails efficiently completing all tasks while considering the capabilities of the available machines. The strategic determination of the sequence in which tasks are processed on diverse machines plays a pivotal role in achieving efficient scheduling.

5.5 Assumptive Processing Method

We also have a simple method to solve our FMS problem in which we assume that all the collisions, like the downtime and the delay, occur in every single combination and hence can be ignored. Based

on the processing times, we add two jobs with the smallest processing time, as the two most minor jobs can be processed together on a single machine. We can remove the two most minor processing time jobs and add the new job, the combined job of the two most minor processing time jobs. Then, we sort the jobs again in the descending order of the

processing time and then assign the most significant processing time job to Machine 1, the average processing time job to Machine 2, and the minor processing time job to Machine 3. In most cases, it gives us the optimal solution, but the drawback is that as the number of jobs increases beyond 5, the accuracy of the method decreases as collisions increase. So, the assumption that all the collisions, like the downtime and the delay, can be ignored is false as the focus shifts from processing time to preventing collisions. Fig. 5 shows the scalability of the algorithm. Fig. 6 shows the time complexity of the algorithm.

Fig. 5 Scalability of the algorithm

Fig. 6 Time complexity of the algorithm.

6 TESTING

The 1-Fold Cross Validation method is used to test the algorithms. In this method, 1 out of 500 records is chosen for testing, and the remaining 499 records are used in training. We use this method for all the 500 records, and then the average accuracy is aggregated for every algorithm. This method provides a better way to maximize data. However, this method is subject to some degree of over-fitting as external data is not considered during the test process. Our proposed algorithms provide consistent and accurate results, which decreases the effect of over-fitting.

7 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Although Fig. 6 shows the time complexity of algorithms, it is evident that the brute force and RNN phase 3 algorithm takes more time than the assumptive processing method. However, in Fig. 5, which shows the scalability of the algorithms, it was observed that when the number of jobs increased, the accuracy of the RNN Phase 1, RNN Phase 2, RNN Phase 3, and Genetic Algorithm remained consistent. However, the accuracy of the Assumptive Processing Method decreases when the number of jobs is greater than 4. Hence, from Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, it was

determined that the assumptive processing method cannot be used for the scheduling due to its critical negative trade between accuracy and efficiency.

Table 2. shows the mean processing time of all the designed algorithms. It was observed that the RNN Phase 1 algorithm obtained a mean processing time of 64.05 minutes as it had to process and simulate multiple input configurations to obtain the output of optimal sequence. The RNN Phase 2 algorithm obtained a mean processing time of 8.04 minutes. However, it provided a pseudo-optimal solution in 14.4% of the 500 input configurations as the number of input configurations was reduced to minimize the processing time. The RNN Phase 3 algorithm obtained a mean processing time of 4.02 minutes as a mathematical equation was used, which reduced the number of input configurations for a given number of jobs to get the output sequence. By not binding the machines and the jobs at the initial stage of the code, much flexibility was achieved, which reduced the makespan further. The Genetic Algorithm obtained a mean processing time of 9.03 minutes as it used a mathematical equation, reducing the makespan compared to its prior implementations seen in the literature survey. Table 3. shows the outcome of the first five records of the input data calculated using the RNN Phase – 3.

Table 2. Mean processing time of all designed algorithms.

Sr. No.	Algorithm:	Mean Processing time:
1	RNN Phase – 1	64.05 minutes
2	RNN Phase – 2	8.04 minutes
3	RNN Phase – 3	4.02 minutes
4	Genetic Algorithm	9.03 minutes

Table 3. Outcome of the first 5 records of the input data calculated using the RNN Phase – 3 algorithm.

Record Number	Output Sequence	Makespan	Processing time
1	J1(M1),J4(M2),J2(M3),J3(M1)	68.4	5.24
2	J1(M1),J4(M2),J3(M3),J2(M2)	89.2	3.8
3	J2(M1),J1(M2),J4(M3),J3(M1)	87	3.38
4	J3(M1),J1(M2),J4(M3),J2(M1)	64.2	4.39
5	J1(M1),J2(M2),J4(M1),J3(M3)	63.8	4.65

8 CONCLUSION

The application of different algorithms to solve the problem of FMS scheduling is discussed in this paper. The FMS environment consists of nonidentical machines with tools stored in a standard tool magazine that shares the tools between the machines. A comparison of the designed algorithms, such as the RNN Phase 1 Algorithm, RNN Phase 2 Algorithm, RNN Phase 3 Algorithm, and Genetic Algorithm based on processing time, was considered. The RNN Phase 3 Algorithm exhibited the lowest processing time while providing consistent optimal results. The RNN Phase 3 Algorithm has a mean processing time of roughly 4 minutes. Table 3. shows the outcome of the first five input data records calculated using the RNN Phase 3 algorithm, which shows the record number, output sequence, makespan, and the processing time.

9 FUTURE SCOPE

Considering the problem mentioned, further study on scheduling jobs for their allocated machines employing automated guided vehicles with multiple objectives can be considered using RNN Phase 3 Algorithm.

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Author 1 and Author 2 contributed equally to this work.

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